

Vanadium XI. Oxo-Vanadium (IV) Heterochelates—I*

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A general synthetic route to oxo-vanadium (IV) heterochelates is described for the first time. A series of complexes of the type $[\text{VO}(\text{AA})(\text{XYX})]$ or of the type $[\text{VO}(\text{AB})(\text{XYX})]$ (where AA = *o*-phenanthroline, κ - κ' -dipyridyl, ethylenediamine, acetyl acetone etc; AB = glycine, picolinic acid, 8-hydroxyquinoline etc and XYX = a tridentate pyridine 2,6 dicarboxylic acid or the related 4-hydroxy pyridine 2,6 dicarboxylic acid or pyridine 2,4,6 tricarboxylic acid) have been synthesised and adequately characterised.

While giving much of our efforts for elucidating the coordination chemistry of oxovanadium (IV)¹⁻⁴, a literature survey promptly exposed that the major complexes are of the type $[\text{VO}(\text{X})(\text{bidentate ligand})_2]$ where X may be H₂O or some amine molecule or none. Such complexes are well known with acetylacetone, quinaldinic acid, hydroxyphenyltriazones, hydroxamic acids and the recently reported pyridine mono-carboxylic acids. A few neutral ligands such as *o*-phenanthroline, κ - κ' -dipyridyl have also been studied recently^{5,6,7}. This does not definitely exhaust the list of the bidentates that have been studied but nevertheless is fairly representative. Besides the above type, a limited few are known where the complex is of the type $[\text{VO}(\text{X})(\text{quadridentate})]$, a few Schiff bases being tried. One recent interesting quadridentate Schiff base is propylenediamine acetylacetone ligand, with which a claim of partial resolution of the oxovanadium (IV) complex has been made⁸. As against all these, very rarely tridentate ligands, in particular, powerful tridentate ligands have been studied. Glycine salicylaldehyde Schiff base is one such example that may be cited in this context⁹.

Our interest in the subject has been exhibited in a number of publications since 1960¹⁻⁴. We were rather surprised to see that the literature has practically no record of heterochelate complexes of oxovanadium (IV)⁶ inspite of the fact that oxo-vanadium (IV) is known to give rise to complexes with very high stability constant values as deter-

*A brief summary of the works described in this and the following paper was presented before the joint convention of the Indian Chemical Society and the C.S.I.R. held at Aligarh Muslim University, December, 1965.

1. Dutta and Lahiri, *J. Ind. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **38**, 1001.

2. Dutta, Ghosh and Lahiri, *Science & Culture*, in press.

3. Dutta and Ghosh, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1966, **28**, 247-49.

4. Dutta, Syamal and Ghosh, in press.

5. Jones, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 5995.

6. Selbin and Holmes, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1962, **24**, 1116, report $[\text{VO}(\text{o-phen}(\text{oxalate}))]$ and $[\text{VO}(\text{dipy}(\text{oxalate}))]$ in unsatisfactory purity.

7. Ray and Banerjee, *Proceedings of the Symposium on the Chemistry of Coordination Complexes, Agra, Part III*, 1959, p.198.

8. Ramalah and Martin, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1965, **27**, 1663.

9. Mukherjee and Ray, *this Journal*, 1955, **32**, 508.

mined by formation constant chemists¹⁰. This paper describes results that will show that this gap has been adequately bridged and a general synthetic route opened to the oxo-vanadium (IV) heterochelates.

A number of working schemes could be conceived so as to lead to such syntheses.

(1) In oxovanadium (IV), the double bonded oxygen evidently takes up one coordination position, so that if one feeds a strong tridentate, dibasic acid $XYXH_n$, then oxo-vanadium (IV) gets a total of four coordination positions and also satisfies its valence requirements. Such a complex will evidently crystallize (being a non electrolyte), say from an aqueous system, possibly with two more aqua molecules thus reaching its usual maximum coordination number of six. This complex might serve as an ideal material for introducing a bidentate ligand inside the coordination zone, replacing the two aqua molecules and in the process giving an oxo-vanadium (IV) heterochelate. The complexes may ultimately have a non-electrolytic nature or turn out to be electrolytes as well depending on the nature of the bidentate ligand that is chosen. The danger of a homochelate being formed by the linking of two tridentate ligands (one of which may under compulsion stay as a bidentate) may be obviated by working at a suitable pH, where the higher homochelate is not formed.

(2) The situation becomes a bit more involved when one desires to have a heterochelate around an oxo-vanadium (IV) having a bidentate ligand. If the formation of a mono-bidentate complex and the bis bidentate complex is favourably regulated by a wide pH difference, it may be possible to have heterochelate complexes. It might as well be possible to start with vanadium (V), reduce that with a ligand which is also a bidentate and controlling the amount of the metal and the reducing ligand may lead to the formation *in situ* of a complex of the type $[VO(\text{bidentate})\text{aq}]$. This solution may then be fed with other bidentates giving rise to a class of heterochelates.

(3) The third approach may lead to heterochelate complexes of vanadium (IV), rather than of oxo-vanadium (IV). If one works with VCl_4 in a perfectly non aqueous solvent (where solvolysis effects might be inoperative), it is quite likely that introducing two bidentates would give complexes of the type $[VCl_2(XY)_2]$ or $[V(XY)_2]Cl$ (where XYH is a monobasic bidentate) or with a bidentate neutral donor $[VCl_2(AA)_2]Cl$ or $[V(AA)_2]Cl$. Similar comparable types will occur also with tridentate and quadridentate ligands $[V(AAA)_2]Cl$, $H[V(XYX)Cl_2]$, $V[(XYX)_2]$ (AAA-neutral donor, $XYXH_n$ is a dibasic tridentate) or $[V(AAAA)Cl_2]Cl$ or other types depending on the acid character of the ligands. Some of these forms will be capable of exhibiting *cis-trans* isomerism (for which there is no report as yet in the literature) and may quite well serve as a route to vanadium (IV) heterochelates. For this third type decidedly the single major factor would be to operate in a perfectly dry atmosphere and with solvents where there would not be any danger of solvolysis occurring leading to an oxo-vanadium (IV) species.

Whereas the third scheme is still in its exploratory stage in our laboratory, we make a report here on the first scheme and the outcome of the second scheme would be reported in the following paper. In an earlier paper we have made a lengthy report on oxo-vanadium (IV) complexes of pyridine mono-, pyridine di- and pyridine tricarboxylic acids. We have therein shown that pyridine 2,6 dicarboxylic acid, 4-hydroxy-pyridine 2,6-dicarboxylic acid and pyridine 2,4,6 tricarboxylic acid do function as tridentate ligands. With the first of these three ligands it was shown from extensive spectral measurements that a 1:1 metal:

10. Trujillo *et al.*, *Chem. Abst.*, 1956, **50**, 16528; 1957, **51**, 11907; 1958, **52**, 1966; 1959, **53**, 21343; 1960, **54**, 2076.

ligand complex persists over a fairly wide pH range and it is quite easy to isolate complexes with one such tridentate ligand and two other aqua molecules inside the coordination zone. These according to our above scheme (I) should serve as ideal materials for the syntheses of heterochelates of oxo-vanadium (IV).

Blue diaquo lutidinato-oxo-vanadium (IV) monohydrate reacts readily in aqueous solution with an alcoholic solution of *o*-phenanthroline to provide chocolate brown crystalline product, which has been identified as a heterochelate [VO(O-phen)(Lut)] H₂O. Similar reaction with κ - κ -dipyridyl or with ethylenediamine, provide yellowish brown crystals or a dirty green granular precipitate identified as [VO(dipy)(Lut)] H₂O or [VO(en)(Lut)]. The complexes are all non electrolytes, give usual magnetic moment values of about 1.8 B.M. indicative of the quadrivalence of vanadium. With bidentate ligands, which are acidic (instead of being neutral like *o*-phenanthroline, κ - κ -dipyridyl or ethylenediamine), the resulting complexes provide some interesting aspect. Of this group, a fairly large number of ligands have been chosen, namely glycine, acetylacetonone, picolinic acid, 8-hydroxyquinoline, benzohydroxamic acid and salicylaldoxime. With acetylacetonone or glycine, bright leaf-green crystals are obtained which have the composition [VO(acacH)(Lut)] and [VO(glyH)(Lut)]. Besides being characterised as heterochelates the slight solubility in aqueous solution brings in further interesting results. One has to decide with regard to complexes of the above sort, whether the acetylacetonone hydrogen and the glycine hydrogen are free, giving rise to such configuration as H[VO(acac)(Lut)] and H[VO(Gly)(Lut)]. Conductance measurements provide a very much lower value, the acetylacetonone giving λ_M value as about 22 ohm⁻¹ and that with glycine only 21 ohm⁻¹. This definitely indicates that there is no substantial release of protons in solution (Table I). This aspect is also supported by measurements of pH of the aqueous solutions, which are almost neutral. A report concerning neutral keto behaviour of acetylacetonone has appeared in the literature^{11a}. A calculation of the pK value based on the above pH measurements place them as very weak complex acids. But both the pH and the conductance of an aqueous solution increased with time and finally reached a steady value after many hours. (Table II and Fig 2). This may be attributed to the reaction:

which ultimately reaches equilibrium. With picolinic acid the situation is not very much different ($\lambda_M=61$ ohm⁻¹). However with 8-hydroxy-quinoline the hydroxy hydrogen is reasonably displaced outside the coordination sphere. The complex H[VO(oxin)(Lut)] registers a high conductance value ($\lambda_M=203$ ohm⁻¹) and also a much lower pH value. These two evidences together indicate that the equilibrium

is substantially to the right. The corresponding pK value also proves this to be a stronger acid compared to the other heterochelates of this same group. Prior to undertaking of the conductance and the pH studies, we decided to measure the

11. Selbin, Ortolano and Smith, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1963, 2, 1315.

11a. Grđnic and Colig, *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, October, 1963.

equivalent weights of these expectedly acidic complexes by running them through a column of strong anion exchanger resin (cl-form) and then estimating the liberated acid (Table III). We observed that the green solutions did not become entirely colourless on one single run through the column, repeated runs ultimately provided a solution free from any green tinge. This evidently pointed to an equilibrium between the acid form and the undissociated non electrolyte form, with the latter prepondering over the other. These complexes are also paramagnetic giving moments close to 1.73 B.M. (Table IV).

TABLE I
Conductance Measurements (in water)

Complex	Dilution (in litres)	128	256	512	1024
[VO(acacH) (Lut)]	λ^0	8.4	18.81	25.25	31.61
	$\lambda \infty$	8.91	19.63	26.00	33.00
	$\lambda \infty$ (mean) = 21.88	Molar conductance = 21.88			
[VO (glyH) (Lut)]	λ^0	8.00	18.70	24.30	31.53
	$\lambda \infty$	8.73	19.60	25.18	31.53
	$\lambda \infty$ (mean) = 21.26	Molar conductance = 21.26			
[VO (picH) (Lut)]	λ^0	31.05	50.91	70.00	83.10
	$\lambda \infty$	32.96	53.10	72.52	84.86
	$\lambda \infty$ (mean) = 60.86	Molar conductance = 60.86			
H [VO (oxin) (Lut)]	λ^0	158.0	183.1	210.08	227.5
	$\lambda \infty$	167.7	191.0	217.7	232.4
	$\lambda \infty$ (mean) = 202.2	Molar conductance = 202.2			

* Calculated using Walden's formula $\lambda \infty = \lambda^0 (1 + 0.692 \sum n_1 x_{n_1} + \sum n_2 x_{n_2}^2 V^{\frac{1}{2}})$ where n_1 and n_2 are the valencies of the ions.

TABLE II
*Conductance Measurements in Methanol (G.R.)
(of non-electrolyte complexes)*

Complex	Concentration	Λ_m in mho
[VO (Lut) (∞ - ∞ -dipy)] H ₂ O	0.001M	1.68
[VO (Lut) (o-phen)] H ₂ O	" " "	2.20
[VO (Lut) (o-phenylenediamine)] H ₂ O	" " "	2.50
[VO (Chel) (∞ - ∞ -dipy)]	" " "	2.10
[VO (Chel) (o-phen)]	" " "	1.88
[VO (CollidH) (∞ - ∞ -dipy)]	" " "	2.8
[VO (CollidH) (o-phen)]	" " "	2.88

TABLE II
pH Measurements

Complex	Concentration	pH (after 3 hours of keeping in solution)	*pK (Calcu- lated from the observed pH)
[VO (acacH) (Lut)]	0.005 N	4.07	5.83
[VO (glyH) (Lut)]	"	4.33	6.35
H [VO (Pic) (Lut)] H ₂ O	"	3.91	3.97
H [VO (oxin) (Lut)]	"	2.93	3.45
H [VO (gly) (chel)]	0.001 (N)	3.58	4.06

TABLE III
 Equivalent weight determination

Complex	Equivalent Weight	
	Found	Calculated
[VO (acacH) (Lut)]	234.6	332
[VO (glyH) (Lut)]	314.7	307
H[VO (oxin) (Lut)]	380.7	377
H[VO (pic) (Lut)] H ₂ O	378.1	373
H[VO (chel) (gly)]	327.0	323

 TABLE IV
 Magnetic measurements

Complex	Dia. (Corr.) × 10 ⁶	λ _m (Corr.) × 10 ⁶	μ _{eff} (B.M.)
Acetylacetonate-lutidinato-oxovanadium (IV) [VO (C ₇ H ₃ NO ₄) (C ₅ H ₈ O ₂)]	131.27	1367.3	1.82
Glycine-lutidinato-oxovanadium (IV) [VO (C ₇ H ₃ NO ₄) (C ₂ H ₃ NO ₂)]	121.78	1359.78	1.81
Oxide-lutidinato-oxovanadium (IV) [VO (C ₇ H ₃ NO ₄) (C ₂ H ₇ NO)]	159.74	1444.74	1.86
Salicylaldehyde-lutidinato-oxovanadium (IV) [VO (C ₇ H ₃ NO ₄) (C ₇ H ₇ NO)]	150.14	1359.14	1.81
α-α'-Dipyridyl-lutidinato-oxovanadium (IV) [VO (C ₇ H ₃ NO ₄) (C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂)] H ₂ O	181.75	1395.75	1.83
Glycine-chelidamate-oxovanadium (IV) [VO (C ₇ H ₃ NO ₄) (C ₈ H ₃ NO ₂)]	125.58	1412.58	1.84
α-α'-Dipyridyl-chelidamate-oxovanadium (IV) [VO (C ₇ H ₃ NO ₄) (C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂)]	185.55	1354.55	1.81
O-Phenanthroline-lutidinato-oxovanadium (IV) [VO (C ₇ H ₃ NO ₄) (C ₁₂ H ₈ N ₂)] H ₂ O	195.57	1417.57	1.84
O-Phenanthroline-collidinato-oxovanadium (IV) [VO (C ₈ H ₃ NO ₄) (C ₁₂ H ₈ N ₂)]	205.37	1367.37	1.81
α-α'-Dipyridyl-collidinato-oxovanadium (IV) [VO (C ₈ H ₃ NO ₄) (C ₁₂ H ₈ N ₂)]	191.97	1438.97	1.8
Acetylacetonate-collidinato-oxovanadium (IV) [VO (C ₈ H ₃ NO ₄) (C ₃ H ₈ O ₂)]	148.67	1362.67	1.81

 TABLE V
 Electronic Absorption spectral Data
 (for solid compounds dissolved in water)

Complex	Band II			Band I		
	λ _{max} mμ	wave no. (cm ⁻¹)	ε	λ _{max} mμ	wave no. (cm ⁻¹)	ε
[VO (acacH) (Lut)]	600 sh*	16600	16.9			
	650	15400	20.5	840	11900	35.0
[VO (glyH) (Lut)]	605	16500	24.8	850	12050	40.2
	606 sh*	15100	26.8			

*sh designates shoulders; these may as well be treated as separate bands.

Besides characterising a large number of heterochelates with pyridine 2,6 dicarboxylic acid, we had also investigated the position with 4-hydroxy pyridine 2,6 dicarboxylic acid (chelH_2) and pyridine 2,4,6 tricarboxylic acid (Collid H_3). With both of these ligands, complexes of the above general types have been isolated. Their conductance, pH and equivalent weight have also been studied wherever possible besides the magnetic moment evaluation (Tables I to III)

The infrared spectra of some of these complexes have also been studied which all show the characteristic vanadyl band around 980 cm^{-1} .

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

The electronic absorption spectra for the complexes have been recorded in aqueous and alcoholic solution, wherever this has been permitted by solubility relation. In these heterochelates we expect only a poor symmetry, lower than C_{2v} and further splitting of the usual bands in oxo-vanadium (IV) complexes is not unexpected. However, we have observed these complexes to furnish two prominent peaks corresponding to two bands and much less pronounced shoulders which may also be regarded as separate bands. In the visible range we covered ($320\text{ m}\mu$ - $860\text{ m}\mu$). Thus $[\text{VO}(\text{acacH})(\text{Lut})]$ shows two bands at $840\text{ m}\mu$ ($11,900\text{ cm}^{-1}$), $650\text{ m}\mu$ ($15,400\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and a shoulder at $600\text{ m}\mu$ ($16,700\text{ cm}^{-1}$). The glycinate complex gives two bands at $830\text{ m}\mu$ ($12,100\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and $600\text{ m}\mu$ ($16,700\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and a shoulder at $660\text{ m}\mu$ ($15,100\text{ cm}^{-1}$). The dipyriddy complexes $[\text{VO}(\text{dipy})(\text{Lut})]\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $[\text{VO}(\text{dipy})(\text{Collid H})]\text{H}_2\text{O}$ are only poorly soluble ($0.0025M$) and therefore, much reliance cannot be placed with the extinction coefficients. Any way the lutidinato compound provides two peaks at $760\text{ m}\mu$ ($13,200\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and $640\text{ m}\mu$ ($15,400\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and the collidinato again two peaks at $770\text{ m}\mu$ ($13,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and $650\text{ m}\mu$ ($15,400\text{ cm}^{-1}$). (Fig. 1). We have thus not been able to find four bands in the visible region as has been the case in a significant recent study of oxo-vanadium (IV) complexes with tartaric acid, lactic acid etc. in an alkaline pH¹²⁻¹³. However, our system responds to usual situation found in many other such complexes¹⁴⁻¹⁶.

12. Ortolano, Selbin and McGlynn, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1964, 41, 262.13. Selbin and Morpurgo, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1965, 27, 673.14. Horner and Tyrce, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, 1, 844.15. Sathyanarayana and Patel, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1965, 27, 297.16. Ballhausen and Gray, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, 1, 111.

EXPERIMENTAL

α-α'-Dipyridil-lutidinato-oxo-vanadium (IV) monohydrate.—[VO (Lut) (H₂O)₂] H₂O (0.3 g) was dissolved in hot water (25 ml) and then cooled in ice to 8-10 and α-α'-dipyridil (0.16 g) in rectified spirit was added to it gradually with stirring when a yellowish brown granular precipitate settles down. The precipitate was digested on steam bath for ½ hr, cooled, filtered and the residue washed several times with rectified spirit and dried over CaCl₂. Then dry product was a yellowish brown crystalline substance, sparingly soluble in hot alcohol. Found: V, 12.48; N, 10.4; H₂O (loss at 105°-110°C) 4.33. Reqd. for [VO (C₇H₅NO₄) (C₁₀H₈N₂)] H₂O: V, 12.56; N, 10.35; H₂O, 4.43%.

Orthophenanthrolin-lutidinato-oxo-vanadium (IV) monohydrate.—[VO(Lut) (H₂O)₂] H₂O (0.3 g) was dissolved in hot water (30 ml) and orthophenanthrolin monohydrate (0.2 g) in rectified spirit (5 ml) was added to it and following the above procedure a chocolate brown granular product was obtained. Found: V, 11.91; N, 9.95; H₂O (loss at 110°C) 4.2. Reqd. for [VO (C₇H₅NO₄) (C₁₁H₈N₂)] H₂O: V, 11.86; N, 9.86; H₂O, 4.18%.

Acetylacetone-lutidinato-oxo-vanadium (IV).—[VO(Lut) (H₂O)₂] H₂O (0.3 g) was dissolved in hot water (10 ml) and acetylacetone (0.15 g) was added to it and the very bright green solution was evaporated on steam bath to a volume of 4-5 ml when bright green crystals appeared. This was then cooled, filtered, washed with acetone and dried over CaCl₂. The dried product was a bright green crystalline solid sparingly soluble in water and alcohol. Found: V, 15.24; N, 4.12. Reqd. for [VO (C₇H₅NO₄) (C₉H₈O₂)]: V, 15.37; N, 4.22%.

Glycine-lutidinato-oxo-vanadium (IV).—[VO(Lut) (H₂O)₂] H₂O (0.6 g) was dissolved in hot water (5 ml) and to it was gradually added a solution of glycine (0.15 g) in hot water (5 ml) and evaporated to a volume of 2-3 ml and excess of rectified spirit was added when a voluminous light green crystalline precipitate was thrown down. This was digested on water bath for 15 min., filtered, washed with spirit and dried over CaCl₂. The dried compound was sparingly soluble in water and alcohol. Found: V, 16.40; N, 8.98. Reqd. for [VO (C₇H₅NO₄) (C₂H₃NO₂)]: V, 16.62; N, 9.12%.

Ethylenediamine-lutidinato-oxo-vanadium (IV).—[VO (Lut) (H₂O)₂] H₂O (0.6 g) was dissolved in hot water (5 ml) and treated with ethylenediamine (0.13 g) and the deep green solution was evaporated to a volume of about 2 ml and excess acetone was added when a dirty green granular precipitate settled down. It was then filtered, washed with acetone and dried over CaCl₂. Found: V, 17.56; N, 14.52. Reqd. for [VO (C₇H₅NO₄) (C₂H₆N₂)] : V, 17.4; N, 14.39%.

Picolinic acid-lutidinato-oxo-vanadium (IV) monohydrate.—[VO(Lut) (H₂O)₂] H₂O (0.3 g) was dissolved in hot water (5 ml), picolinic acid (0.14 g) was added to it and the solution was evaporated to dryness on steam bath. The residue was then dissolved in minimum cold water and excess of anhydrous methanol was added when a greenish black precipitate was thrown down, filtered, and washed with methanol. During washing the compound turns gummy. It was then repeatedly triturated with acetone, filtered and dried over CaCl₂. The dried product was sparingly soluble in alcohol but highly soluble in water. Found: V, 13.78; N, 7.49; H₂O (loss at 105°) 4.7. Reqd. for [VO (C₇H₅NO₄) (C₆H₅NO₂)] H₂O: V, 13.68; N, 7.51; H₂O, 4.82%.

O-Phenylenediamine-lutidinato-oxo-vanadium (IV) monohydrate.—[VO (Lut) (H₂O)_n] H₂O (0.3 g) was dissolved in hot water (10 ml) and to it was added a solution of *o*-phenylenediamine (0.12 g) in hot water (5 ml) and the solution was evaporated on steam bath to a small volume (5 ml) when a brightgreen crystal appeared. It was then cooled, filtered and washed with alcohol and dried over CaCl₂. Found: V, 14.36; N, 11.61; H₂O (loss at 120°) 4.9. Req'd. for [VO (C₇H₈NO₄) (C₆H₈N₂)] H₂O: V, 14.24; N, 11.73; H₂O, 5.02%.

Benzohydroxamic acid lutidinato-oxo-vanadium (IV).—[VO (Lut) (H₂O)_n] H₂O (0.3 g) was dissolved in hot water (10 ml) and solution of benzohydroxamic acid (0.14 g) in water (5 ml) was added to it when the solution gradually turned violet. It was kept in a refrigerator for 3-4 hr. when emeraldgreen needles mixed with violet powdery substance were deposited. It was filtered, washed with alcohol (in which the violet substance was soluble) until the washings are colourless and finally dried over CaCl₂. Found: V, 14.00; N, 7.70. Req'd. for [VO (C₇H₈NO₄) (C₇H₇NO₂)] : V, 13.87; N, 7.01%.

Oxin-lutidinato-oxo-vanadium (IV).—[VO (Lut) (H₂O)_n] H₂O (0.3 g) in minimum hot water and rectified spirit (15 ml) was treated gradually with oxin (0.14 g) when a greenish brown solution was obtained which after evaporation to dryness was triturated with acetone, filtered and washed with acetone and dried over CaCl₂. It was a navy-blue granular solid soluble in water. Found: V, 13.58; N, 7.43. Req'd. for [VO (C₇H₈NO₄) (C₉H₇NO)] : V, 13.52; N, 7.42%.

Salicylaldoxime-lutidinato-oxo-vanadium (IV).—[VO (Lut) (H₂O)_n] H₂O (0.3 g) in hot water (10 ml) was treated with a methanolic (25 ml) solution of salicylaldoxime (0.14 g) and the solution was evaporated to a small volume on steam bath, cooled and treated with excess acetone when a deep blue precipitate settled down. It was filtered, washed with acetone and dried over CaCl₂. The dried product is soluble in water. (Found: V, 13.68; N, 7.8. Req'd. for [VO (C₇H₈NO₄) (C₇H₇O₂N)] : V, 13.85; N, 7.68%.

O-Phenanthroline-chelidamato-oxo-vanadium (IV).—Chelidamic acid (0.18 g) and vanadyl sulphate pentahydrate (0.25 g) were dissolved in boiling water (15 ml) and orthophenanthroline monohydrate (0.2 g) in rectified spirit (5 ml) was gradually added to it with stirring when a granular light brown precipitate was thrown down. It was digested for 15 min. on steam bath, cooled, filtered, washed with spirit and dried over CaCl₂. Found: V, 11.49; N, 9.50. Req'd. for [VO(C₇H₈NO₄) (C₁₀H₈N₂)] : V, 11.42; N, 9.41%.

α-α'-Dipyridil-chelidamato-oxo-vanadium (IV).—This was obtained as a yellowish brown granular solid following the above procedure using dipyridil (0.16 g) instead of orthophenanthroline. Found: V, 12.57; N, 10.24. Req'd. for [VO (C₇H₈NO₄) (C₁₀H₈N₂)] : V, 12.63; N, 10.40%.

Dimethylglyoxime-chelidamato-oxo-vanadium (IV).—A solution of chelidamic acid (0.18 g) and vanadyl sulphate pentahydrate (0.25 g) in boiling water (10 ml) was treated with dimethylglyoxime (0.12 g) in alcohol (5 ml) and the solution concentrated on steam bath until crystals appeared. It was then cooled, filtered, washed with alcohol and dried over CaCl₂. The dried product was a crystalline yellowish brown solid. Found: V, 12.65; N, 10.60. Req'd. for [VO (C₇H₈NO₄) (C₄H₈N₂O₂)] : V, 12.75; N, 10.71%.

Orthophenylenediamine-chelidamato-oxo-vanadium (IV).—Chelidamic acid (0.18 g)

and vanadyl sulphate monohydrate (0.18 g) in hot water (10 ml) was gradually treated with a solution of orthophenylenediamine (0.12 g) in hot water (5 ml) and concentrated on steam bath until green crystals appeared. It was then cooled to room temperature, filtered, washed with alcohol and dried over CaCl_2 . Found: V, 13.52; N, 11.31. Reqd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{NO}_2)(\text{C}_6\text{H}_6\text{N}_2)]$: V, 13.63; N, 11.23%.

Glycine-chelidonio-oxo-vanadium (IV).— $[\text{VO}(\text{Chel})(\text{Py})(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$ (0.34 g) was suspended in 40 ml hot water and gradually treated with glycine (0.08 g) and evaporated to dryness on water bath. The residue is dissolved in water (5 ml) and again evaporated on steam bath when the absence of pyridine odour indicates the complete removal of pyridine. The residue was again dissolved in minimum water, cooled and excess rectified spirit was added when an olive green granular precipitate appeared. It was filtered, washed with spirit and dried over CaCl_2 . Found: V, 15.68; N, 8.57. Reqd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_3\text{NO}_2)(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{NO}_2)]$: V, 15.70; N, 8.67%.

Orthophenanthroline-collidinato-oxo-vanadium (IV).— $[\text{VO}(\text{CollidH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ H_2O (0.33 g) in hot water (10 ml) was gradually treated with a solution of orthophenanthroline monohydrate (0.2 g) in alcohol (5 ml) when a granular light brown precipitate was thrown down. It was digested on waterbath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr, cooled, filtered, washed with alcohol and dried over CaCl_2 . Found: V, 11.21; N, 9.15. Reqd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{NO}_4)(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2)]$: V, 11.19; N, 9.21%.

α - α' -Dipyridil-collidinato-oxo-vanadium (IV).—This was obtained as a yellowish brown granular solid following the above procedure using α - α' -dipyridil in place of orthophenanthroline. Found: V, 11.68; N, 9.68. Reqd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_5\text{NO}_5)(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2)]$: V, 11.80; N, 9.72%.

Acetylacetone-collidinato-oxo-vanadium (IV).— $[\text{VO}(\text{CollidH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ H_2O (0.33 g) was dissolved in hot water (10 ml) and treated with acetylacetone (0.14 g) and evaporated on steam bath until deep green crystals appeared. It was then cooled, filtered, washed with alcohol and dried over CaCl_2 . Found: V, 13.39; N, 3.60. Reqd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_3\text{NO}_6)(\text{C}_5\text{H}_8\text{O}_2)]$: V, 13.49; N, 3.70%.

Orthophenylenediamine-collidinato-oxo-vanadium (IV).— $[\text{VO}(\text{CollidH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ H_2O (0.33 g) dissolved in boiling water (10 ml) was treated with a solution of orthophenylenediamine (0.12 g) in hot water (5 ml) and the solution concentrated on steam bath till green crystals appeared. It was then cooled, filtered, washed with alcohol and dried over CaCl_2 . Found: V, 13.18; N, 11.02. Reqd. for $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{NO}_6)(\text{C}_6\text{H}_8\text{N}_2)]$: V, 13.28; N, 10.93%.

General Experimental Methods. Vanadium was estimated as V_2O_5 after igniting the complex. Nitrogen was estimated by semimicro Dumas technique.

Equivalent weight was determined by running the aqueous solutions of the complex species through an anion exchanger (IR, 400 A Cl-form) and finally estimating the liberated acid. The equivalent weight was given by:

$$E. W. = \frac{W \times 36.5}{V \times S \times 0.001825}$$

where W = Weight of the complex taken.

V = Volume of alkali required for titration.

S = Strength of alkali used in N/20.

0.001825 = Wt. of HCl per ml. of N/20 HCl

36.5 = mol. wt of HCl.

Absorption spectra was recorded in a Uvispek spectrophotometer using 1 cm cell and conductance by a Phillips conductivity Bridge, and pH by Cambridge pH meter.

Magnetic susceptibility was determined by a Gouy Balance using G.R. copper sulphate pentahydrate (E. Merck) as the calibrant. Magnetic moment was calculated from the relation

$$\mu_{\text{eff}} = 2.84 \sqrt{\lambda_M \cdot (\text{corr.})} \times T \text{ BM}$$

where T = absolute temperature.

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